

The Cult of the Fox

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The "cult of the fox" is not a cohesive religious group. Instead, the name refers to a variety of relationships and interactions between humans and fox spirits in a range of accounts, most of the zhiguai 志怪 ("records of the strange") genre. Accordingly, the cult of the fox can be considered part of Chinese "popular" or "folk" religion, itself a general term used to refer to various religious practices in China at the local level and outside of the major traditions of Confucianism, Daoism, and Buddhism. Fox spirits are known by many names, but are most frequently referred as huxian 狐仙. The cult is regional by nature and, in the 16th-20th centuries, was primarily located in the modern day provinces of Shaanxi, Shanxi, Hebei, Henan, Shandong, Northern Anhui, and Jiangsu. These areas form the focus of this entry. In addition, there were sporadic mentions of the fox cult in Southern China and fox worship has been present in Manchuria from the 19th century to the present-day. Even further afield, fox worship can be found in both Korea and Japan, though a detailed study of those areas and the relationship of their worship to Chinese practices is outside the bounds of this entry. Generally speaking, there is no distinction made between huxian ("invisible fox spirits") and living foxes as the latter are considered to be spiritual animals. In many instances, it is said that foxes are long-lived and that by cultivating themselves and learning secret arts over the course of their lifetimes they can become huxian. Because neither the fox cult nor the larger context of Chinese popular religion are closed, centrally-organized systems, huxian are thought to exist alongside a host of other human and non-human spiritual entities, including the ghosts of deceased humans, Daoist deities and immortals, gods and spirits from other popular traditions, and Buddhist Bodhisattvas and Buddhas. Within this array of spiritual entities, huxian are understood as liminal, and often subversive, figures, a trait that makes them perfect figures for negotiating and mediating between different forces and domains. Fox worship is thus highly personal in nature and humans can form a variety of different relationships with foxes. Accordingly, foxes are associated with complex family dynamics (often involving wives and daughters) and are frequently worshipped by marginalized groups such as prostitutes and entertainers. Most commonly, huxian are associated with spirit mediums, particularly female mediums, who have generally had little social status in the late imperial period, despite their services being sought out by all social classes. Although huxian can, at times, bring families wealth and prosperity (though not always via moral means), they are frequently understood as dangerous, vengeful, and even malign tricksters. Many huxian accounts describe them as possessing humans, seducing humans for sport, and even subjecting humans to forcible sexual encounters. The sexual aspect of huxian has also led to their frequent association with female sexuality, conceived of as potentially dangerous to systems of patriarchal control. Indeed, the colloquial term "fox essence" (hulijing 狐狸精), which arises from fox cult practices, denotes the dualism of an enchanting woman's sexual potency and powers of lustful destruction in many literati works and popular lore up to the present. The liminal and sexual aspects of the huxian, as well as the potential for the personal concerns animating their worship to challenge established hierarchies, meant that their worship was frequently proscribed by the state. However, even suppressed, their worship served as a vital source of support and efficacy outside of official religious channels, especially with respect to private or even criminal concerns. In a number of cases, huxian are also domesticated and integrated into more conventional or orthodox systems. For example, stories about huxian brides frequently depict paragons of Confucian virtue who transform sexual and dangerous female huxian into demure brides. Similarly, huxian are sometimes associated with larger, more mainstream cults such as the Queen Mother of the West and

even Guanyin, the Boddhisattva of compassion. Perhaps the most dramatic case is in the latter part of the Qing dynasty when huxian worship was used by state officials as a strategy for pacifying disturbances. As a result, huxian shrines were included in yamen offices and the huxian was even declared the "great guardian of the official seal." Huxian worship persists to this day in contemporary China. It continues to include spirit mediums and to occupy the marginal position that it has held throughout the centuries of the late imperial period.

Date Range: 1500 CE - 1950 CE

Region: North China

Region tags: Jiangsu Province, Shandong, Shaanxi Province 陕西省, China, Hebei, Shanxi, Northern Anhui, Henan Province, Anhui

Area in which the cult of the fox was widespread during the late imperial period. The modern provinces of this area are Shaanxi, Shanxi, Henan, Hebei, Jiangsu, Shandong, and northern Anhui.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Because the cult of the fox was not a separate religious group, interactions between humans and huxian were intertwined with other religious traditions, including other cults belonging to Chinese folk religion (e.g. City God worship), Buddhism, Confucianism, and Daoism. Depending on the specific circumstances, this intertwining could take on different forms (see the examples in the sub-questions below).

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: At times, fox worship could infringe on other cults or practices. For example, sexually active fox women were thought to vie "with other local deities for people's offerings and remained a potential threat to the established gods" (Kang 2006, 133). An 18th century account by Fang Yuankun (fl. 1799), for instance, describes a situation in which a female fox spirit was married by the local villagers to the earth god. Although the villagers treated the fox as she were subordinate to the earth god, in practice her worship in the village far outstripped that of the earth god (Kang 2006, 134-137). As well, Daoist priests frequently sought to exorcise foxes through the "Five Thunder Rites" and state officials at times suppressed fox worship in favour of officially-sanctioned worship and in an effort to control local society (Kang 2006, 128-129; 168-170).

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Foxes were sometimes thought to form cooperative relationships with other cult figures. For example, as early as the Han dynasty, "the fox was believed to be an attendant of the Queen Mother of the West, a female deity of local shamanistic origin," though this link disappeared in later time periods (Kang 2006, 141). Later, the fox was associated with two other gods: Mother Taishan (also known as Bixia) and Granny Wang. These female deities were at times also associated with Buddhism and the Bodhisattva, Guanyin, indicating the fluid nature of different cults and traditions of worship (Kang 2006, 141-147). Finally, the fox was at times worshipped as part of the five sacred animals (Kang 2006, 146) and, in the late Qing, officials would even worship foxes as the "Great Guardians of the Official Seal" (Kang 2006, 185-189).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Fox worship could readily exist alongside other religious practices without being influenced by them or disrupting them.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Fox worship was varied and could be both public and personal. There was thus no defined group to control or assign religious affiliation.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Fox worship was varied and could be both public and personal. There was thus no defined group to engage in proselytization.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: In general, foxes were considered social threats and were associated with undesirable elements of society such as courtesans, prostitutes, entertainers, wanderers, and outlaws (Kang 2006, 161-170). Accordingly, the worship of foxes was often suppressed and "officials often acquired expertise in exorcistic rites and invoked the powers of celestial bureaucrats for help" (Kang 2006, 170). However, in the late Qing, "the worship of foxes was widely adopted as a familiar strategy for officials to pacify disturbances." The fox was even named the "great guardian of the official seal" and fox shrines were included in official yamen offices. While the worship of the fox was not "prescribed by imperial law," it had "all the power of law" as officials were forced to confront the local power of popular fox cults (Kang

2006, 185-189).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Fox worship was varied and could be both public and personal. There was thus no defined group from which one could be considered an apostate.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: The fox cult existed alongside a wide variety of other cults and religious traditions that varied in scale.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Because fox worship did not occur within a cohesive group, there was no organized hierarchy of religious leaders. However, spirit mediums were frequently associated with fox spirits as figures of authority (despite being looked down upon as a class) because they enabled foxes and mortals to communicate (Kang 2006, 97-126).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The local and non-cohesive nature of fox worship meant that it was not associated with any particular religious texts and did not have any scriptures. Moreover, many accounts of foxes were included in zhiguai 志怪 (records of the strange) anthologies, which were not considered religious scriptures. However, fox spirits were often involved in spirit writing and so "revelations by fox spirits became a source of vernacular stories and cryptic texts" that could be associated with secret societies or sects (Kang 2006, 60).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Fox shrines were frequently small and could be included inside other temples, including Buddhist temples or earth god temples (Kang 2006, 147-159; 133-137). They could also be inside yamen offices and inside bedrooms (Kang 2006, 189).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Fox shrines could be set up in any location.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: This question is answered yes because Chinese popular practices, of which the cult of the fox was a part, included a belief in ghosts. Similarly, accounts of fox spirits suggest fox spirits can take immaterial, spirit-forms that can possess the physical bodies of mortal humans. However, this aspect is not emphasized in accounts of fox spirits, nor do those accounts provide systematic theorizations

regarding the spirit-body distinction.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– No

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Descriptions of fox encounters sometimes include the presence of deceased human ghosts, suggesting the belief in an afterlife. At the same time, fox worship could be intertwined with larger traditions such as Daoism and Buddhism, which both included conceptions of the afterlife (such as the underworld bureaucracy in Daoism and purelands and hells in Buddhism). However, fox worship did not delineate or define its own afterlife as distinct from other traditions.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: The influence of Buddhism led to a widespread belief in reincarnation. For instance, the Xingshi yinyuanzhuan, a vernacular novel that appeared sometime between 1628 and 1728, includes a story of a fox who was killed and reincarnates as a woman to take revenge on the killer (Kang 2006, 63). However, reincarnation was not emphasized in most accounts of foxes.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Notions of reincarnation were derived from Buddhism and so necessarily included the idea of karma upon which those ideas were based.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Fox worship did not include specific burial practices.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Fox worship did not include specific burial practices.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Fox worship did not include specific burial practices.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Fox worship did not include specific burial practices.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts" (gui 鬼), the remains of deceased humans, are accepted presences within Chinese popular religions. At times, foxes could be associated with ghosts because the term gui is a broad one and can refer to demons, monsters and "other kinds of malign force" (Kang 2006, 73). Ghosts were typically understood as dangerous entities and some were even described in vampiric terms as siphoning the life energies of human beings in order to replenish themselves (Kang 2006, 74). In order to propitiate potentially dangerous ghosts, the living were required to conduct food offerings (Kang 2006, 74).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes

Notes: Ghosts were dependent on the food offerings of the living, typically their descendants. Accordingly, food offerings were the "determining factor in securing the reciprocal relationship between living descendants and ancestors." In addition to their ancestors, people would also leave out food for wandering ghosts in order to "prevent them from pilfering the offerings made to the deceased." At times, fox spirits would

also pilfer the offerings made to deceased ancestors and, in some accounts, families would offer food to foxes in order to domesticate them and transform them into benevolent protectors of the family, akin to the role played by the family ancestors (Kang 2006, 78).

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: As defined in this entry, the main feature of the "cult of the fox," is the presence of fox spirits, referred to by a variety of names but most commonly as huxian 狐仙. Fox spirits were not considered distinct from ordinary, living foxes. Instead, foxes were thought to be spiritual and long-lived entities who could cultivate themselves over time in order to gain magical powers. These included the ability to change their shape, become human, cure illnesses,

absorb human essence (usually through sexual intercourse), and even become transcendentals (Kang 2006, 55). A distinctive feature of fox spirits is their highly individual natures. Fox spirits exhibit a range of complex emotions and possess their own personalities, identities, names, and agendas. This personal quality also extends to the nature of the relationships that foxes formed with humans. For example, mediums, who often acted as the main communicative link between humans and foxes, typically served a specific fox with a specific name who initiated them into medium practice (Kang 2006, 98-102). In addition, foxes could form a variety of relationships with humans, playing the role of temptresses, lovers, wives, husbands, and friends (Kang 2006, 197). The personal character of fox worship also meant the cult could be considered quite dangerous, not because of its personal aspect per se, but because of the potential for the personal concerns animating it to challenge established hierarchies (Kang 2006, 197).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Although at times fox spirits can be invisible, at other times they can be seen and touched as physical presences.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Although at times fox spirits can be invisible, at other times they can be seen and touched as physical presences.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Foxes are mobile and transgressive figures and so their knowledge is not limited to a particular domain of human affairs.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Fox knowledge is restricted in the sense that foxes are not considered omniscient. However, the mobility of foxes, as well as their magical abilities means that their knowledge is not restricted to a specific location.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Fox knowledge is not unrestricted in the sense that foxes are not

considered omniscient. However, the mobility of foxes, as well as their magical abilities means that their knowledge is not restricted to a specific location and so, in this sense, might be considered "unrestricted."

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The fact that foxes can be invisible and possess magical powers means that their ability to see humans far exceeds what mortal humans might be capable of.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Arts of transcendence and other cosmic areas

Notes: Because foxes are long-lived and cultivate themselves to achieve magical powers and become transcedents, they have a much greater knowledge of the cosmos than mortal humans.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: For more detailed discussions of fox spirits' ability to reward and punish living

humans, see the comments below in the "supernatural monitoring" subsection.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Fox spirits are complex and multi-faceted and so exhibit a range of emotions, both positive (such as generosity or attachment) and negative (such as anger, jealousy, and lust).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Fox spirits are complex and multi-faceted and so exhibit a range of emotions, both positive (such as generosity or attachment) and negative (such as anger, jealousy, and lust).

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Like ghosts, foxes must be fed through offerings of food if a human wishes to establish a reciprocal relationship with them. If they are not propitiated with food offerings, foxes may pilfer the offerings left to other entities, such as ancestral spirits (Kang 2006, 78-79). Moreover, since foxes are considered a form of life (as opposed to ghosts who are an intangible form of death) and are not considered distinct from ordinary foxes, they necessarily have similar needs as mortal humans (Kang 2006, 75).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Magical powers and sexuality

Notes: A key feature of foxes is that they cultivate themselves through arts of transcendence and so achieve magical powers, which is what enables them to perform the supernatural deed with which they are credited. As well, sexuality is an important dimension of fox spirits and is emphasized in accounts of both male and female foxes. With respect to their sexuality, foxes range from seducing humans into sexual encounters to subjecting humans to forcible sexual encounters (Kang 2006, 83-88; 129-133).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Because neither the fox cult nor the larger context of Chinese popular religion are closed, centrally-organized systems, huxian are thought to exist alongside a host of other human and non-human spiritual entities, including the ghosts of deceased humans, Daoist deities and immortals, gods and spirits from other popular traditions, and Buddhist Bodhisattvas and Buddhas. However, the defining feature of the cult of the fox (as discussed in this entry) is the presence of fox spirits, not other supernatural beings. Accordingly, the subsequent sections are answered only with respect to fox spirits and not to other deities or spirits that the same individuals might encounter.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Foxes are frequently described as living in families ("dens") and, in some accounts, are organized into larger kinship structures. In these structures, fox patriarchs are described as wise, Daoist masters, who watch over their descendent foxes and intercede on their behalf with other celestial figures (Kang 2006, 131).

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Foxes typically occupied a space outside of the celestial bureaucracies that organized other deities and maintained personal relationships with those they encountered. However, they could be placed in formal, hierarchical structures such as when officials in the late Qing worshipped male foxes (named the "guardians of the official seal") in a way that presented them as mirror figures to "Daoist divine transcendentals and celestial bureaucrats" (Kang 2006, 197). Similarly, foxes were sometimes described as coming under the authority of other celestial hierarchies. For example, some accounts describe foxes as subordinate to the goddess Bixia (Mother Taishan) whose control over them was imagined in bureaucratic terms so that foxes "in pursuit of transcendence would take examinations, equivalent to the civil service examinations, under the supervision of Mother Taishan" (Kang 2006, 139).

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Notes: Although other deities of Chinese popular religion could be associated with specific domains of the cosmos, fox spirits were generally not confined to a specific aspect or domain. Instead, they were liminal figures who could appear in a variety of settings and contexts.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Ritual

Notes: Rituals of propitiation, particularly in the form of food offerings, were the principal means by which different organizations of spirits and ghosts were maintained. For example, the ghosts of deceased relatives could be positioned as ancestors through the offering of food. Similarly, foxes could be propitiated through domestic food offerings and so come to occupy the same role as human ancestors (Kang 2006, 78). In other instances, foxes could be venerated alongside other deities, such as the Earth God, and could thus come to occupy a comparable role as those deities. The relationships between foxes and other entities could be conceived of in different ways, for instance a female fox spirit could be married to a male Earth God, but the mechanism by which these relationships and roles were made to function was through ritual (Kang 2006, 133-137). Consequently, the organization of supernatural entities, including fox spirits, was often highly fluid and reliant on the ongoing ritual practices of the living.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: Fox spirits do not act as monitors or enforcers of ethical norms according to a defined religious or social code. However, fox spirits could punish and reward mortal spirits based on their personal interactions with them. Accordingly, these punishments and rewards were based on how humans interacted with fox spirits as opposed to their adherence to codified social norms.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Although they were generally not thought of as agents of a larger moral system, fox spirits are frequently described as punishing those mortals who have wronged them in some fashion. Similarly, harming a fox could bring misfortune even when the specific fox spirit that was harmed was not the agent of that misfortune. For example, in one account, a man named Sifter Zhang offered food to a fox spirit in order to make it a benevolent protector of the Zhang family. After using the fox to become prosperous, however, Zhang killed the fox so that, when he died, he would not have to compete with the fox for offerings from his descendents. Subsequent to Zhang's breaking the rule of reciprocity, his house burned down, his second son committed murder and died in prison, and a plague wiped out the rest of the Zhang family, all of which was considered to be retribution for killing the fox (Kang 2006, 78-79). In addition to acts of punishments, many fox accounts emphasize the dangerous nature of fox spirits and the misfortunes they visit upon humans. These misfortunes, however, are not necessarily considered punishments.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Although many different supernatural beings were considered capable of punishment, the cult of the fox under consideration in this entry was primarily concerned with punishments conducted by fox spirits themselves.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: In some instances, harm to a fox resulted in disasters not explicitly linked to a fox. For example, when Sifter Zhang killed a fox that he had previously propitiated, his subsequent misfortunes were considered retribution but the fox spirit itself was not described as the agent of those misfortunes (Kang 2006, 78-79).

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Generally speaking, humans encountered punishments when they wronged or harmed a fox spirit in some way. Punishment was, therefore, not connected to larger moral systems, but to the persons of the fox spirits themselves.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The dangerous nature of foxes and the possible consequences of mistreating them are running threads in many different fox spirit accounts.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: As discussed in the comment above, the Zhang family lost their home to fire after their head harmed a fox spirit he had previously propitiated (Kang 2006, 78-79).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

Notes: In one account, a named named Gao kills dozens of foxes while hunting. Later, two beautiful maidens convince him to rebel against the emperor. The rebellion is quickly crushed and the man capture. The two women were believed to be avenging foxes punishing the man for his killing of other foxes (Kang 2006, 160). Foxes were also known to hinder local officials' efforts at law and order. Foxes are frequently described as invading and haunting yamen offices and causing minor disturbances in them through actions such as theft, harassment and arson (Kang 2006, 174-180).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: As discussed in the comment above, the Zhang family was destroyed through plague when their head harmed a fox that he had previously propitiated (Kang 2006, 78-79). In general, the ability to cause illnesses was one of the major magical powers that foxes were believed to possess (Kang 2006, 55).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

Notes: Despite their frequent association with sexuality, foxes were generally not related to fertility.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: As discussed above, when the head of the Zhang family harmed a fox whom he had previously propitiated, his second son committed murder and died in prison (Kang 2006, 78-79).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Foxes were able to punish humans in a variety of creative ways, such as murdering a person's family members, possessing their family members, and subjecting them to forcible sexual encounters.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: As in the case of punishments described above, humans received rewards from foxes when they treated foxes well, such as by offering them food, or because the fox favoured them in some way. As such, rewards were not necessarily tied to a larger moral system, but to the relationships that existed between foxes and humans.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Although many different supernatural beings were considered capable of rewarding humans, the cult of the fox under consideration in this entry was primarily

concerned with the rewards received from fox spirits themselves.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Although individuals would propitiate foxes in order to receive rewards from them, many accounts of fox spirits seem less concerned with the rewards humans receive and more concerned with how the liminal figure of the fox enables humans to negotiate complex relationships and societal obstacles.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: Foxes could be a source of prosperity for humans, though not always by moral means. For example, one account describes how a family formed a relationship with a fox who would steal for them whatever they required and so made them very prosperous. As the fox remarks to one of the descendants, "I have made your family enjoy wealth and happiness for generations" (Kang 2006, 83-84). The ambiguity of this story is underlined by the fact that the fox initially caused the family much suffering and sexually deluded the wife of the family head.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: In the account of a man named Zhao Sunyi, his close relationship with a fox woman (whom he served as if she were his parent) enabled him to gain an official post (Kang 2006, 81). Moreover, as "great guardians of the official seal," foxes were thought to assist the officials who sacrificed to them in controlling unruly areas and securing political power (Kang 2006, 185-189).

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: In line with their ability to cause illness and disease, fox spirits could also cure the illnesses of mortal humans (Kang 2006, 55).

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

Notes: Despite their frequent association with sexuality, foxes were generally not related to fertility.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: As discussed in the comment above, long-lived foxes could attach themselves to

specific families and so provide benefits for the descendants of the person with whom they initially formed a relationship (Kang 2006, 83-84).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Although not necessarily fitting a narrow definition of "reward," the personal ties between foxes and humans could provide a means for the resolution of complex, personal issues. For example, in one account a man named Zhao Sunyi acted in an unfilial way to his parents who died of poverty. He subsequently met a fox woman who claimed to be his father's mistress and, by serving her "dutifully as a filial son," Zhao was able to "relive the past experience of parental care and repay it with due respect and devotion" (Kang 2006, 81).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Because it was not an organized or cohesive religious group, the cult of the fox did not advocate a codified set of ethical precepts or norms. However, as liminal figures encountered in the course of daily life, fox spirits were heavily involved in negotiating the ethical and normative complexities of late imperial society.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Because it was not an organized or cohesive religious group, the cult of the fox did not advocate a codified set of ethical precepts or norms. However, as liminal figures encountered in the course of daily life, fox spirits were heavily involved in negotiating the ethical and normative complexities of late imperial society.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Because it was not an organized or cohesive religious group, the cult of the fox did not advocate a codified set of ethical norms or virtues. However, as liminal figures encountered in the course of daily life, fox spirits were heavily involved in negotiating the ethical and normative complexities of late imperial society.

imperial society.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Fox worship entailed food offerings such as wine, as well as incense candles, which were the property of those worshipping the fox spirit in question (Kang 2006, 189).

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Food offerings

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Though not conducted in public or communal settings, fox propitiation required that worshippers present offerings to, and pray before, fox shrines, which would necessarily require a small amount of time.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Although those who encountered foxes did not necessarily refer to each other using kinship terms, humans could at times refer to fox spirits themselves using kinship terminology, such as "grandpa" (ye 爺) or "Divine Aunt" (xiangu 仙姑) (Kang 2006, 94).

Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– I don't know

Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– I don't know

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The two major polities of the late imperial period, the Ming and Qing empires, were highly centralized, bureaucratic empires that ruled over multi-ethnic populations. Because this entry primarily focuses on the fox cult during the late imperial period, the questions and comments of the subsequent questions refer to these polities and not to the successor states of mainland China during the 20th century.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In theory, famine relief was the purview of the central government during the Ming and Qing empires.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Temples of larger religious traditions, such as Buddhism, frequently provided poverty relief. At times, the Ming and Qing central governments might do the same as well.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Private and public educational institutions were present in both the Ming and Qing empires.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects or have a formal structure.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained formal bureaucracies with which members of the fox cult would have interacted.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained institutions for public food storage.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained institutions for water management.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained institutions for infrastructure management.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained formal taxation systems to which members of the fox cult would have been subject.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained judicial structures, enforced by institutionalized police forces, with which members of the fox cult would have interacted.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained judicial structures to which members of the fox cult would have been subject.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained judicial structures that included institutionalized punishments to which members of the fox cult would have been subject.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained formal legal codes to which members of the fox cult would have been subject.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained formalized military institutions.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Ming and Qing empires maintained formalized military institutions.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Literate individuals who interacted with fox spirits would have had access to the same written Chinese as all other individuals living in the Ming and Qing empires during the late imperial period.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Dynastic empires, such as the Ming and Qing, provided formal calendars for their subjects' use.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Because it was not a cohesive or formal religious group, the cult of the fox did not engage in collective projects. However, those who interacted with foxes could include those who provided for their own sustenance.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– I don't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Xiaofei Kang. *The Cult of the Fox: Power, Gender, and Popular Religion in Late Imperial and Modern China*. New York: Columbia University Press.